

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE USE OF EDUCATIONAL CLUSTER IN EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES: AN EXAMPLE OF HISTORICAL SCIENCE

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Abstract: *This article discusses the forms, methods and technologies for achieving the effectiveness of education by ensuring continuity and continuity in the educational process of using cluster technology in teaching historical subjects in general education institutions. The use of various techniques when conducting history lessons in chronological order, including: chronological links, pre-professional links, synchronous links, informative links, etc. forms with are called.*

Keywords: *continuity, connections, forms, curriculum, standard, competence, cluster, synchronous communications, pre-professional communications, educational and methodological support, historical emblems.*

In the teaching of the subject of history, science is determined by the formation of relations and the peculiarity of ensuring the continuity associated with its implementation, the basis of Science, the structure and content of the subject of study, its purpose and role in the DTS, program, curriculum. Each educational science, including history, consists of a separate system of knowledge - evidence, understanding, a specific logical connection of ideas. Students master them through the formation of an internal system of connections between all forms of reflection of the object reality. In creating such links, the course plays a special role in the education cluster, in which contacts play an important role. Bunda defines that the students' knowledge gained during the year is logically intertwined with each other, that they can finish school with state educational standards and competences that can meet the requirements of consumers, as well as the successful transition to the next stage of Education.

It is possible to distinguish the following forms of conducting history lessons in harmony with the course:

1. Chronological (retrospektiv) relations– the appeal to students who rely on the educational material known earlier from both history courses in

explaining the new subject (for example, “the emergence and development of the Arab Caliphate” - “the culture of the caliphate countries”).

2. Perspektiv communication-to apply in advance to the materials provided for in the future systematic study. (Chunchi, the history of mankind-the fact that ideas consist of history.

3. Synchronous relations-the simultaneous (corresponding) occurrence of the study of two subjects that are close in content in the courses of history, or events that occur simultaneously (for example, in the third period of the Middle Ages “culture of European peoples” and “science and cultural life in the Timurian period”, the world-wide significance of the culture of the Timurian period).

4. Informative relations are Relations at the level of theoretical, historical evidence and concepts, which are categorized into:

5. Relations in the stylistic description are formed by the students ' perception of the world as a result of studying historical facts on the history of the world and Uzbekistan, their perception of the holistic essence of the development of society through reflection, their generalized clear images are reflected in their broad concepts and principles and ideas on the worldview (for example, the leading ideask.).

6. Relations with activities are carried out in the system of skills and skills. (for example, creative thinking, educational-communicative, organizational, bibliographic, etc. skills and qualifications). The focus of this developmental education lies in the formation of the general and integrated ability and thinking of the individual towards the achievement of the goal through education. In addition, the students ' course of clarifying historical knowledge provides for a number of skills specific to this subject: analysis of historical material in time and space, comparison, etc. [1].

Increasing the effectiveness of the lesson on the basis of the educational cluster requires the application of various forms and methods of education in the educational process to practice. In order for students to actively engage their knowledge and perceive the material with the help of course links in a short period of time, the educator will have to go from simple methodological methods to complex ones. These are the following in the sentence: mention (examples, citing evidence, etc.)k.), assignment and questions (logical, problematic, etc.k.) give, compare, historical journey (look at the history, travel to the past), create different tables, pass an integration course by combining the topics of the course, summarize the newly studied material by analyzing it by linking it with a known material (historical concepts) from another course, passing a course on the basis of new pedagogical technology, passing a course using additional resources, summarizing – use of course links in repetition lessons, etc.

The development of integrated education is associated with the proper, pedagogical-based learning of the form and content of Education, which requires an in-depth analysis of educational, educational, developmental goals.[2]

It is desirable to bring questions and assignments in the educational provision in the use of interrelations with the help of various assignments and questions. Indeed, the development of the ability of students to base their conclusions by analyzing historical material related to linkstirishga is aimed at "logical observation!" the following questions and assignments given under the rukni will be addressed: what do you think is the cause of the appreciation of European rulers from Amir Temur, who ended the Battle of Ankara with victory? What is the impact of Uzbek culture on India during the baburids? Comment on the following phrase, which was popular in the Middle Ages in the East: "Samarkand is the land of sayqali, Islam of the power of Bukhara is religious".

The method of comparison plays an important role in the formation of students' imaginations of time and space, bringing them to understand the essence, causes and consequences of historical events, events and processes. "Russian pedagogue K.D.Ushinsky believed that the comparison of the phenomena studied was the most important method used in didactics"[3]. In the process of teaching historical courses in this direction, the following can be compared::

1) objects of one kind (monuments of material-spiritual culture, historical-geographical objects), connected to one time or different historical epochs;

2) a kind of events and events that took place in different countries at different times, their causes and consequences;

3) events and events that take place at the same time in one country or in several countries, similar to each other as well as different from each other;

4) the processes of social development in different countries, similar or identical to each other.

The implementation of the on-site lessons through the historical educational games in the world and the history of Uzbekistan will yield good results. In the system of forms and methods of teaching history, educational games occupy a special place. It is one of the components of a new pedagogical technology, the use of educational games creates the basis for the development of students' independent logical thinking skills and the search for knowledge.

Historical educational games can be divided into two groups.

To the first group it is possible to include small historical games for 2-6 pupils: problematic games, chewing gum, finding the answer to

chronological tasks, historical Lotto, correct answers to various quiz questions, etc.

The second group includes historical competitions, workmanship, figurative games, which require the participation of all students in the class, sometimes several classmates. Among these, historical alligator games are one of the types of educational games in which students organize their cognitive activities in a team style and have their own characteristics. In particular, during this game, students perform past and modern events imagined on the basis of the plot of the game, as well as logos distributed to them, through game actions aimed at a specific goal.

The fact that students have a good knowledge of historical conditions, analyze the causes and significance of the events under study, as well as the ability to understand the essence in depth, are considered an important factor that will ensure the success of this game. At the same time, it is also important that the teacher prepares students psychologically for the game. For the purpose of using this game in a generalizing lesson on the subject of history, students are given the following task: present-day fiction writers put forward the idea of creating a volatile time technique that will convey the future to the desired countries and periods. Imagine that you have the opportunity to travel to the country you wanted in the Middle Ages in the technique of time. So, make a flying program in the "flying time technique" and attach importance to the following::

1. Indicate the Century(year) you want to go.
2. Tell me the name of the country in which you want to go.
3. Choose for yourself what historical symbol you want to fulfill during the journey:
 - a) modern man (historian, scientist, pupil, writer, Artologist, etc.k.);
 - b) a representative of the medieval period (poet, scientist, craftsman, merchant, peasant, commander, nobleman, Khan, Minister, tax collector, etc.k.).
4. Base the century(Year), country and symbol of your choice.
5. Determine the purpose of your trip. Make a story statement about what you saw at the end of the trip. Depending on the purpose of the trip, describe in the declaration the labor and fighting weapons, appearance of people, as well as monuments of architecture, works of art of this period, the description, description of outstanding historical figures, which you were able to meet during the trip, enter the conversation you had with the people of that period.

In history education, synchronous (simultaneous, mutually compatible) communication and relations that are consistent with past events can be carried out in different ways. In particular, the completion of synchronous and integral chronological tables according to the instruction

of the teacher systematizes the knowledge of students about some kind of historical framework that exists in the history courses.

The system of chronological dates, in which interconnected and interrelated proportions are determined, helps to thoroughly master historical evidence, creating a chronological basis in the minds of students. In particular, the study of continuous chronological and synchronous relationships, including through the repetition and strengthening of course-based relationships, determines the specific nature of history teaching[4].

The cluster approach to history lessons allows the institution's governing bodies to provide certain tools for effective interaction within the system, better understanding of the problems, planning the scientific basis for the development of effective teaching of historical sciences in the Region[5]

So, in conclusion, we can say that by integrating the content of Education, exemplary norms of evaluation should be developed in accordance with the requirements of consumers, taking into account the existing problems in the acquisition of knowledge, skills and qualifications of students in the teaching of historical sciences. It was also recommended to develop the main criteria for the selection of methodological methods for the purpose of increasing the effectiveness of the lesson by interrelating the courses of history. Bunda it is necessary that the integration of the content and methods of Historical Sciences on the basis of the laws applicable in the educational process and the scientific pedagogical principles arising from it is determined by the capabilities of the teacher and students.

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